

Observational Study about Knowledge and Awareness of Personal Hygiene among Patients at a Upazila Health Center in Bangladesh

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Abstract

Background: The majority of Bangladesh's population has access to clean drinking water in both urban and rural areas, but the quality of that water is harmed by bacterial contamination brought on by unsanitary practices, the presence of unfavorable chemical contamination like arsenic, and seawater intrusion brought on by climate hazards. This study was carried out to determine whether patients at Upazila Health Complex in Savar, Bangladesh, were aware of certain personal hygiene and sanitation issues.

Methods: This observational research was carried out in the Upazila Health Complex in Savar, Bangladesh, from November 20 to November 28, 2023. The purpose of the study was to assess certain personal hygiene habits among adult Savar Upazila Health Complex patients. The research comprised 204 patients in all, ranging in age from 18 to 60 and coming from both urban and rural locations. The sample technique employed was convenience sampling. Utilizing a semi-structured questionnaire, data was obtained.

Results: About 20.58% were age group 18 to 28 years, 26.96% were age group 29 to 40 years of age and 52.45% were from age group 41 to 60 years. Most of the respondents said that they usually used tap water which is substantial amount of 60%. From this study, it was found that, most of the population 50% use sanitary latrine for convenience and low cost to build a sanitary facility. About 77% of them washed hands with soap while another 2% did not washed hands after defecation. In this study majority of the respondents (nearly half) had moderate knowledge about proper hygiene and punctuality. 24.51% possess poor knowledge about sanitation and awareness for better health.

Conclusion: Education on good hygiene, both in urban and rural areas, is essential to lowering the prevalence of infectious illnesses. Improved encompassing seminar and campaign of these problems should be used to be affordable, and it will be very successful initiatives that would significantly reduce the incidence of communicable diseases among patients in rural areas.

Keywords: Knowledge; Defecation; Handwash; Sanitary facility; Hygiene

1. Introduction: Pit latrines without slab coverings, hanging latrines, and bucket usage are examples of inadequate sanitation facilities. It is also considered unacceptable to defecate

outside. There is a great deal of variation in the shared sanitation practice, suggesting that different sanitation methods could be more useful for catering to the needs of different people [1]. Individual, family, community, and national health are all directly impacted by poor sanitation. Use of latrines, personal hygiene, a clean environment, appropriate disposal of solid and liquid waste, and hygienic conduct are all considered elements of sanitation [2]. Improved general health standards, labor force productivity, and a high level of living all depend on proper sanitation [3]. More than 80% of diseases in poorer nations are caused by contaminated water and poor sanitation [4].

It is generally accepted that improved sanitation and hygiene practices are beneficial in reducing illnesses and controlling the spread of germs [5, 6]. The importance of promoting the best sanitation and hygiene practices has been affirmed by international policy documents and global pledges. The United Nations (UN) said that access to better sanitation and adequate hygiene practices is likely to produce sustainable economic growth and a brighter future under the Sustainable Development Goals (SGD target 6) [7]. Research indicates that low-income countries have a relatively low adoption rate for maintaining excellent hygiene habits, even though it is well-established that improved sanitation and hygiene practices in learning environments are effective [8].

In Bangladesh, almost one-third of the people are living in poverty [9]. A third or higher of the poorest people defecate outside [10]. Bangladesh is confronted with several obstacles concerning water, sanitation, and hygiene [11]. Lack of knowledge about the advantages of a secured latrine is the primary obstacle to the success of sanitation coverage. Poverty, a shortage of space, and a propensity for open-air defecation are some additional challenges [12]. According to the study, all parties involved should make a concentrated effort to educate students, instructors, patients and health care providers about hygienic conduct. Both the general public and patients need to be more aware of the need of sanitation. Additionally, the study suggests that patients' understanding of cleanliness needs to be enhanced.

2. Methodology: From November 20 to November 28, 2023, this observational study was conducted at the Upazila Health Complex in Savar, Bangladesh. The study's goals were to evaluate specific personal hygiene practices among adult patients at Savar Upazila Health Complex. In all, 204 patients with age range between 18 to 60 from both urban and rural areas were included in the study. Convenience sampling was the method used for sampling. Utilizing a semi-structured questionnaire, data was obtained. Data processing involves categorizing of data, coding and summarizing the data with the help of calculator and Microsoft excel software. A team of two research assistants was sent into the field to gather data for a qualitative study. Every participant in the qualitative study was selected with a specific goal in mind. Participants actively participated, knowing that any personal information they contributed would be kept private and that the data they provided would be utilized responsibly. After organizing the responses into general categories, they were examined. The various positions or opinions were identified once the responses were organized. The analysts synthesized the themes and summed up the differing viewpoints. This article was reviewed by ethical approval committee of Jahangirnagar University with approval number of (JU-4640), and all the information of respondents were kept private.

3. Results: All the findings were analyzed and tabulated to represent all the percentage along with main results. In all, 204 patients with age range between 18 to 60 from both urban and rural areas were included in the study. Convenience sampling was the method used for sampling.

Table 1: Overview of study populations, (Total frequency, N=204)

Variable	Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	94	46.07%
	Female	110	53.93%
Age group (years)	18 - 28	42	20.58%
	29 - 40	55	26.96%
	41 - 60	107	52.45%
Religion	Islam	179	87.74%
	Hinduism	25	12.26%
	Christian	0	0%
Residents	Urban	125	61.27%
	Rural	79	38.73%

Figure 1: Gender distribution among population

Table 2: Available water sources for patients use

Type of source	Available percentage
Self-purchased drinking water	24%
Tap water	60%
Deep tube well	7%
Filter machine	9%
Total sources of water = 18	

Table 3: Distribution of respondents according the type of latrine used

Type	Frequency	Percentage
Sanitary latrine	102	50%
Modern toilet	89	43.63%
Open field defecation	13	6.37%

Figure 2: Cleanliness of different types of toilets at health complex

Table 4: Hand washing practice among respondents

Handwashing practice	Percent (approx.)			Number of Respondent
	With soap	Without soap	Do not wash	
After defecation	77%	21%	2%	204
Before meal	53%	46%	<1%	
After work	27%	58%	15%	

Table 5: Habit of brushing teeth

Variable	Frequency (N=204)	Percentage
Daily two times	66	32.35%
Daily one time	134	65.68%
At interval	4	1.96%

Table 6: Knowledge about importance of sanitation at critical times

Level of Knowledge	Frequency	Percentage
Enough	54	26.47%
Moderate	100	49.02%
Poor	50	24.51%

4. Discussion: Participants gave their consent and actively engaged, understanding that their contributions would be kept confidential and used appropriately. The replies were analyzed after being grouped into broad groups. Following the organization of the replies, the distinct stances or viewpoints were recognized. The analysts summarized the contrasting opinions and synthesized the topics. About 20.58% were age group 18 to 28 years, 26.96% were age group 29 to 40 years of age and 52.45% were from age group 41 to 60 years. Approximately 46% were male and 54% were female, 87.74% respondents belong to Islam and 12.26% were Hindu (Table 1).

Most of the respondents said that they usually used tap water which is substantial amount of 60%. On the other hand, 24% uses self-purchased water from local market and shops and it cost a lot. 7% were for deep tube well and 9% used filter machine to drink more safe water for better health concern (Table 2).

In case of latrine usage by all the respondents, it was found that, most of the population 50% use sanitary latrine for convenience and low cost to build a sanitary facility. While, 43.63% used modern toilets as they are from urban areas and 6.37% defecate in open field (Table 3).

Handwashing practice of respondents at their home was observed during data collection. (Table 4) shows that about 98% of the patients washed their hands after defecation at home and outside. About 77% of them washed hands with soap while another 2% did not washed hands after defecation. It is worth mentioned that still around 15% of the populations do not wash hand after work. About 99% of them washed hand with either water or soap before taking breakfast and less than 1% people did wash hands during taking meal.

It was found that, most of the respondents 65.68% brush their teeth one time a day, 32.35% people brush two times daily for maintaining good hygiene and to avoid bad breath. Only 4 respondents told they are irregular to clean mouth and brush their teeth at intervals and sometimes miss their duty (Table 5).

In this study majority of the respondents (nearly half) had moderate knowledge about proper hygiene and punctuality. 24.51% possess poor knowledge about sanitation and awareness of better health (Table 6).

Based on these results, it appears that the hygiene practices which require the largest amount of water result in lower rates of practice. Both bathing and hair washing require relatively larger volumes of water. The low frequencies of hand washing with soap may be attributed to the lack of soap at home. Soap, water and latrines are essential for proper hygiene practice in rural

people [13]. Examining the hand-washing habits of patients at home and at work is one of the study's goals. According to another study, a certain discrepancy between the impression and actual practice of washing hands with soap might lead to a decrease in the frequency of hand washing before to eating [14]. Improved sanitation and awareness about medicine usage is essential that lead to better society and health [15].

In Bangladesh, there is still more work to be done until everyone has universal access to clean water and sanitary facilities, in spite of the notable advancements made in the WASH sector. The government has to keep making investments in this field a top priority, especially in rural regions where access to clean water and sanitary facilities is a necessary. Furthermore, for the sector to continue making progress and to solve the remaining difficulties, stakeholders—including the commercial sector and civil society organizations—need to continue working together [16]. Even though the majority of people have access to a toilet, only 28% of households have a hand washing station with soap and water, and 40% of individuals utilize communal, subpar sanitation facilities. Water bodies are still contaminated by feces that causes gastric diseases with nutritional anomalies inside bodies [17-20]. Access to clean drinking water is a human right, and good sanitation upholds persons' dignity. For the sake of human health, environmental sustainability, and economic development, freshwater ecosystems must be managed properly, and people must have access to clean water and proper sanitation. The basic principle of sustainable development is access to clean water and sanitation, which are essential for human and environmental existence. The study suggests using a coordinated effort and knowledge to educate the general public and health care practitioners about sanitary behavior that involves all relevant stakeholders.

Limitations of study: This study was conducted on a small patient population in a single-care hospital. More research is required to elucidate these issues as well as sanitary practices, lifestyle choices, patient behavior, and adherence to healthcare duties.

5. Conclusion: In order to provide high-quality water and sanitation services, the government and development partners must step up their efforts. The WASH segment does not receive a sufficient amount of funding from the national budget. Stronger agency accountability in addition to increased funding allocations are necessary to meet WASH targets. Education on good hygiene, both in urban and rural areas, is essential to lowering the prevalence of infectious illnesses. Improved encompassing seminar and campaign of these problems should be used to be affordable, and it will be very successful initiatives that would significantly reduce the incidence of communicable diseases among patients in rural areas.

Disclosure of conflict of interest

None declared.

Ethical consideration

Participants actively participated, knowing that any personal information they contributed would be kept private and that the data they provided would be utilized responsibly.

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